

A Bacteriological Study of Various Culture Samples among Patients Attending Tertiary Care Hospital, Morbi, Gujarat

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Received: 07-07-2024 / Revised: 10-07-2024 / Accepted: 17-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: India face significant risks from infections with multi-drug resistant (MDR) bacteria, which are linked to antibiotic overuse and misuse. The antibiogram profiles of bacteria isolated from infections in patients of tertiary care hospital Morbi were determined in this study.

Methods: A hospital-based cross-sectional study was done between February 2024 and June 2024. Various clinical specimens were sampled from patients and analysed for aerobic bacterial isolation and Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion susceptibility testing.

Results: From the 239 clinical specimens processed, 61 (25.5%) were culture-positive for aerobic bacterial pathogens. Culture-confirmed positivity was higher in urine (29.03%), pus (28.95%) and blood (24.39%) samples. *Escherichia coli* 18 (29.51%) and 16 (26.23%) of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from Gram-negative bacteria were the predominant bacterial isolates, while *Staphylococcus aureus* 12 (19.67%) and *Staphylococcus sp.* 3(4.92%) were from Gram-positive bacteria. Overall, 72.1% of the isolates were found to be MDR. The proportion of MDR among *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus sp.*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was 100%, 100%, 93.75%, 50% and 33.3% respectively. Gram-positive bacteria demonstrated resistance rates of 58.3%, 40%, 37.5%, 35.7% and 29.4% for cefoxitin, gentamicin, azithromycin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, respectively. While Gram-negative demonstrated resistance rates of 85.7%, 75%, 69.7%, 66.7%, 65.9%, 61.8%, 61.1%, 60.5% were recorded for ampicillin cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, cefoperazone piperacillin/tazobactam, ceftazidime, ampicillin/sulbactam, ciprofloxacin respectively.

Conclusion: The main problem is infections caused by bacterial isolates, resistant to most antibiotics. With an alarmingly high number of MDR isolates, the majority of the bacteria that were found to be resistant to the commonly used medicines. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing should therefore be used as a guide for treatment decisions and physicians should use reason when selecting medicines.

Keywords: bacterial isolates, clinical specimen, antimicrobial resistance, antimicrobial susceptibility.

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Introduction

Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) occurs when bacteria, viruses, fungi and parasites no longer respond to antimicrobial medicines. Drug resistance makes antimicrobial medications, including antibiotics, ineffective and makes treating infections challenging or impossible.

This raises the risk of infection spread, serious illness, disability, and death. [1] Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the top global public health and development threats. According to estimates, bacterial AMR caused 4.95 million fatalities worldwide in 2019 and was directly responsible for 1.27 million deaths. [2] AMR is a natural process that happens over time through

genetic changes in pathogens. Human activities have hastened its emergence and spread. The misuse and overuse of antimicrobials in humans, animals and plants are the main drivers in the development of drug-resistant pathogens. [1]

The 2022 Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (GLASS) [3] report highlights alarming resistance rates among prevalent bacterial pathogens. Median reported rates in 76 countries of 42% for third-generation cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* and 35% for methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* are a major concern. For urinary tract infections caused by *E. coli*, 1 in 5 cases exhibited reduced susceptibility to standard

antibiotics like ampicillin, co-trimoxazole, and fluoroquinolones in 2020. This makes treating common infections more difficult. Projections by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) [4] indicate an anticipated twofold surge in resistance to last-resort antibiotics by 2035, compared to 2005 levels, highlighting the pressing need for improved global surveillance coverage and strong antimicrobial stewardship practices.

According to ICMR, in India, sensitivity of organisms such as to antibiotic drugs such as Imipenem carbapenems is decreasing, MRSA rates are increasing each year from 2016 to 2021 (28.4% to 42.6%). 5 In India *Escherichia coli* was the most commonly isolated pathogen followed by the *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. [5] They are also the current most serious antibiotic-resistant organisms. [6] As a result of the high burden of infections, irrational use of antibiotics, over-the-counter availability of drugs and limitations in the availability of antimicrobial susceptibility testing, drug resistance is a major challenge in low-income countries [7,8] Early detection and response at local and regional levels is one of the major strategies recommended to mitigate the spreading of AMR. Understanding and acting on the local or national AMR situation is critical to gaining consensus on implementing appropriate interventions. [9] Therefore, this study was done to identify bacteria and determined their antibiotic resistance profiles from different body site infections at local level that occurred among patients at tertiary care hospital.

Material and methods

Study Design, Period and Setting:

A Cross-sectional study was done for data of period between 1st Feb 2024 to 30th June 2024 i.e. last six months data of patients in tertiary care hospital Morbi. The hospital delivers medical services to all regular and referral cases from the region as well as rural hospitals attached to it. It is equipped with a laboratory for clinical biochemistry, microbiology and pathology test analysis.

Specimen Collection, Processing and Identification

Clinical specimens such as pus, urine, ear discharge, blood, stool, urethral or cervical discharge, sterile fluid and CSF were sampled following standard operating procedures. Depending on the source of specimen, each sample was plated onto blood agar, nutrient agar, MacConkey agar, xylose lysine deoxycholate agar, chocolate agar and incubated aerobically at 37°C. Standard phenotypic microbiological techniques were used to identify the bacterial isolates.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

Susceptibility of bacterial isolates to different antibiotics was analysed by Kirby–Bauer disk diffusion susceptibility testing on Muller Hinton Agar. All the identified bacterial isolates were checked for susceptibility using antibiotic disk for common antibiotics as per current CLSI M100 guidelines.

Quality Control

Prior to data entry, the generated data were examined for consistency, clarity, accuracy, and completeness. Correct laboratory test findings were produced by adhering to standard bacteriological protocols.

Data analysis

Data was entered and analysed using WHONET software and Microsoft excel and basic descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution were calculated.

Results

A total of 239 patient specimens were collected and processed from eight different samples. Of this Blood was 123 (51.5%), Urine 62 (25.9%), Pus 38 (15.8%), Cerebrospinal fluid 6 (2.5%), Sputum 4 (1.7%), Pleural fluid 3 (1.3%), Vaginal swab 2 (0.8%), Stool 1 (0.4%). Among the total samples, 123 (51.5%) were taken from male patients the rest were from female.

Bacterial profile of Isolates

Overall, 61 (25.5%) of the specimens collected were culture-positive and all of them were single isolates. From the total 61 positive patients, the proportion of bacterial isolates in male was 28 and in female it was 33.

Figure 1: Distribution of Bacterial Isolates from all cultures

Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Pneumoniae, Staphylococcus aureus were the most frequently isolated bacteria from the clinical specimen.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristic and Culture-Positive Status of Patients.

Gender	Total N (%)	Culture Result		Isolates Gram-Reaction	
		Positive N (%)	Negative N (%)	Gram negative N (%)	Gram Positive N (%)
Female	116 (48.5 %)	33 (54.1 %)	83 (46.6 %)	25 (58.1 %)	8 (44.4 %)
Male	123 (51.5 %)	28 (45.9 %)	95 (53.4 %)	18 (41.9 %)	10 (55.6 %)

Antimicrobial Resistance Profiles of Bacterial Isolates

Gram-negative bacteria and Gram-positive bacteria accounted for 43 (70.49 %) and 18 (29.51 %) of the isolates, respectively.

Five Gram-positive bacteria were isolated from clinical specimens i.e., Streptococcus pneumonie, enterococcus sp., staphylococcus aureus, staphylococcus coagulase negative, staphylococcus sp. Overall, 18 (29.51 %) Gram-positive bacteria were resistant to the tested antibiotics. Resistance rates of 58.3%, 40%, 37.5%, 35.7% and 29.4% were recorded for cefoxitin, gentamicin,

azithromycin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, respectively. While all of them were 100% susceptible to tetracycline. Five different Gram-negative bacteria were isolated from clinical specimens i.e., Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Acinetobacter baumannii, Salmonella Typhi. Overall, 43 Gram-negative bacteria were resistant to the tested antibiotics. Resistance rates of 85.7%, 75%, 69.7%, 66.7%, 65.9%, 61.8%, 61.1%, 60.5% were recorded for ampicillin cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, cefoperazone piperacillin/tazobactam, ceftazidime, ampicillin/sulbactam, ciprofloxacin respectively.

Table 2: Antimicrobial Resistance Profiles of Gram-Positive Bacterium Species.

Antibiotics	Staphylococcus aureus			Staphylococcus sp.			Enterococcus sp.			Staphylococcus, coagulase negative			Streptococcus pneumonie		
	N	R	S	N	R	S	N	R	S	N	R	S	N	R	S
Azithromycin	12	3	8	3	2	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Cefotaxime	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Cefoxitin	10	5	5	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ceftriaxone	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1

Ciprofloxacin	11	5	6	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Clindamycin	12	0	9	3	3	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
Erythromycin	12	2	1	3	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
Gentamicin	11	5	6	3	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
Levofloxacin	11	2	8	3	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Linezolid	12	3	5	3	0	3	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
Nitrofurantoin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tetracycline	12	0	12	2	0	2	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	12	0	10	3	0	3	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0
Vancomycin	12	0	1	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0

#N= number of isolates tested against each antibiotic, R- resistance, S- susceptible

Figure 2: Showing Susceptible Staphylococcus aureus, Escherichia coli and Klebsiella pneumoniae isolates to various antibiotics

Table 3: Antimicrobial Resistance Profiles of Gram-Negative Bacterium Species.

Antibiotic name	Escherichia coli			Klebsiella pneumoniae			Pseudomonas aeruginosa			Salmonella Typhi			Acinetobacter baumannii		
	N	R	S	N	R	S	N	R	S	N	R	S	N	R	S
Amikacin	18	8	6	16	12	3	6	0	5	0	0	0	2	0	2
Ampicillin	18	18	0	14	12	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	2
Ampicillin/Sulbactam	18	8	6	16	14	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
Aztreonam	16	11	4	13	7	5	6	1	4	0	0	0	2	0	2

Cefepime	16	11	4	15	11	2	6	1	5	0	0	0	2	0	2
Cefoperazone	1	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cefotaxime	17	14	1	16	13	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0
Cefotaxime/ Clavulanic acid	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ceftazidime	15	12	3	11	8	3	6	1	5	0	0	0	2	0	2
Ceftriaxone	16	12	4	14	11	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	2
Ciprofloxacin	18	15	1	16	10	3	6	1	4	1	0	0	2	0	2
Gentamicin	18	9	7	16	12	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
Imipenem	18	7	9	16	11	1	6	1	5	1	0	0	2	0	2
Levofloxacin	14	12	1	13	6	6	6	1	4	1	0	0	2	0	2
Meropenem	17	6	10	16	12	3	6	1	5	1	0	1	2	0	2
Nitrofurantoin	14	2	10	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Piperacillin/ Tazobactam	17	13	2	16	13	1	6	1	4	0	0	0	2	0	2
Tetracycline	18	7	5	16	2	13	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	2
Tobramycin	17	8	5	15	14	1	6	1	3	0	0	0	2	0	2
Trimethoprim/ Sulfamethoxazole	18	10	8	16	8	8	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	2

#N= number of isolates tested against each antibiotic, R- resistance, S- susceptible

Multi-Drug Resistance Profiles of the Isolates

From the total isolates, 14 (23 %) were susceptible to all the tested antibiotics. The majority (77 %) of isolates were resistant to one or more antimicrobials tested. In general, 44 (72.1%) of bacterial species were MDR. The rate of MDR was 100, 100, 93.7, 50, 33.3 among escherichia coli, staphylococcus sp., klebsiella pneumoniae, staphylococcus aureus, pseudomonas aeruginosa respectively. From total isolates 39.3% were possible XDR and 4.9% were possible PDR.

Discussion

One fourth of the total culture was positive for bacterial isolates. Gram-negative isolates were found predominantly higher than gram positive isolates. Which was similar to findings in India [10] and various other parts of world [11–13]. The prevailing isolation of Gram-negative bacteria might be due to higher number of urine samples in this study, might also be due to their simple nutritional requirements, frequent existence in the clinical setting.

In this study, E. coli was the most predominant isolate. This is similar to studies from other parts of India [5,14–16] and world [17–20] This may be brought on by the prevalence of E. coli in UTIs, as well as the bacteria's virulence factors and host-microbe interactions. Furthermore, and Klebsiella pneumoniae and Staph. aureus were the other frequently isolated organisms in the present study. The finding was similar to studies in India, 5,15 other parts of world. [19–22]

In the AMR surveillance data for the year 2023, the most commonly isolated priority pathogen was E. coli (33%), which is similar to the previous year's data [5,15], followed by Klebsiella species

(20%), S. aureus (15%), Pseudomonas species (12%) and findings of current study in 2024 are similar. The prevalence of the aforementioned isolates may be attributed to their frequent presence in hospital environments, which is a significant factor in the increased risk of infections at various body sites and cross-contamination among patients. Furthermore, E. Coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, and S. aureus are common inhabitants of the human skin and digestive tract. They can be transferred from their natural environment to other sterile locations and apertures on the skin and soft tissues, leading to the spread of infection and severe consequences.

Gram-positive bacterial isolates of the present study demonstrated higher resistance to cefoxitin, gentamicin, azithromycin, ciprofloxacin and erythromycin which was similar in AMR surveillance data of India for the previous year's [5,15,23] and other countries of world [19,21,24,25].

Gram-negative bacterial isolates, of the present study demonstrated a high percentage of resistance to ampicillin (85.7%), cefotaxime (75%), ceftriaxone (69.7%), cefoperazone (66.7%), piperacillin/tazobactam (65.9%), surveillance of data by ICMR showed highest resistance in isolates from all specimen types was observed to the antibiotic ampicillin, which was similar to finding in this study. This might be linked with the widespread use of these antibiotics commonly in clinical settings. Since these antibiotics are readily available and affordable, they are frequently used in the community.

The majority 77 % of isolates were resistant to one or more antimicrobials tested which was similar to different parts of India. [5,15,23,26,27] The

majority 72.1% of the bacterial isolates of the present study were MDR. Other studies in India reported 96.0% of the pathogens were MDR in northern India and 83.0% in Haryana, India [29] which were higher than current study's findings while lower proportion of MDR isolates were reported in other parts of the world [12,19,25]. This revealed that antibiotic resistance especially MDR is a rising threat in India. This may be connected to improper use, abuse, and overuse of antibacterial agents. Therefore, the nationwide AMR surveillance is right step towards combating antimicrobial resistance and additional it warrants implementation of invitro susceptibility testing at private and government hospitals with strict adherence to antibiotic policy to inhibit the spread of drug-resistant microbes in India.

Conclusion

Escherichia coli, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were the predominant isolates from various culture samples. Most of the isolates were resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, cefoperazone, piperacillin/tazobactam and cefoxitin. Concurrently, the rates of multiple drug-resistant isolates and possible XDR isolates are alarmingly high. Therefore, it is advised that hospitals implement stringent standards for the use of antibiotics, assist physicians in making informed decisions about the course of treatment, and periodically update their list of approved medications.

Disclosure

The authors declare that they have no competing interests in this work.

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